

DETERMINATION OF THE SOLUBILITY PRODUCT OF NICKEL HYDROXIDE

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Solubility of nickel hydroxide in a number of solutions of hydrochloric acid and in buffer solutions of acetic acid and sodium acetate (1:1) was determined gravimetrically. The p_H of each of the saturated solutions was also measured. From these results the solubility product of nickel hydroxide (K_{sp}) was calculated in both the cases. The most probable value of K_{sp} is considered to be 1.0×10^{-16} .

Britton reported the solubility product of nickel hydroxide to be 8.7×10^{-16} . He used hydrogen electrode in the potentiometric titration of nickel chloride with caustic soda (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2110). Gayer and Garrett reported the solubility product of nickel hydroxide as 6.5×10^{-15} (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 2973) from the solubility of nickel hydroxide in hydrochloric acid. Hence, it was considered worthwhile to measure the solubility product afresh.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Dry nickel hydroxide was prepared as described earlier (this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 735). The solubility experiments of nickel hydroxide in HCl were performed in triplicate by continuous shaking at room temperature (24° - 26°) for one week which was considered to be enough by preliminary experiments. After shaking, the excess of nickel hydroxide was allowed to settle and the supernatant liquid was filtered through a G₄ glass sintered funnel by applying pressure over the solution. The concentration of the nickel in the solution was gravimetrically determined in duplicate with dimethylglyoxime. The weight of the precipitate in the six determinations did not differ by more than 0.0098 from the mean value. The p_H values of these solutions having the same concentration, measured with a Marconi p_H meter (type T F 511D), did not differ by more than 0.02 from the mean value. The experimental values are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Conc. of HCl (initial).	Conc. of nickel in sat. soln.	$f \pm$.	$a_{Ni^{2+}} \times 10^3$.	p_H .	$a_{OH^-} \times 10^7$.	$K_{sp} \times 10^{16}$.
0.0189 g. mol./litre	0.00954 g. mol./litre	0.6033	0.570	7.11	1.301	1.0
0.0757	0.03844	0.4594	1.740	7.07	1.187	2.4
0.1135	0.05772	0.4198	2.382	7.08	1.010	2.4
0.1513	0.07714	0.3967	3.002	6.88	0.766	1.8
0.1892	0.09501	0.3528	3.338	6.80	0.637	1.3

Mean $K_{sp} = 1.8 \times 10^{-16}$

The concentration of nickel in all the solutions studied was slightly more than half the initial concentration of the acid used. Hence, the possibility of the formation of the basic chloride as a precipitate is ruled out and the presence of some nickel hydroxide in the solution is established.

Another set of solubility of nickel hydroxide was carried out in buffer solutions of acetic acid and sodium acetate (1:1). The experimental procedure was the same. The shaking was done at room temperature (28°-30°) for the same period. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Conc. of acetic acid (initial).	Conc. of nickel in sat. soln.	β .	$f_{\pm}^{\dagger}$.	$a_{Ni^{2+}} \times 10^2$.	pH .	$a_{OH^-} \times 10^7$.	$K_{sp} \times 10^{16}$.	
0.040 g. mol./litre	0.020 g. mol./litre	0.675	0.4835	0.653	7.11	1.301	1.1	
0.080	0.040	0.550	0.4231	0.931	7.09	1.243	1.4	
0.120	0.060	0.470	0.3934	1.110	6.95	0.900	0.9	
0.160	0.080	0.415	0.3825	1.272	6.89	0.784	0.8	
0.200	0.100	0.375	0.3730	1.398	6.85	0.715	0.7	
Mean $K_{sp} = 1.0 \times 10^{-16}$.								

DISCUSSION

Solubility in Hydrochloric Acid Solution.—Activity of the hydroxyl ion is calculated from the pH of the solution taking K_w to be equal to 1.01×10^{-14} . The concentration of the nickel ion in solution is taken to be equal to half the concentration of the acid used, and not the concentration of nickel found experimentally. The amount of nickel in excess of the initial acid is due to the presence of the free nickel hydroxide. The activity coefficient of nickel ion at a particular ionic strength is calculated on the same basis as in an earlier paper (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 169). The values of $a_{Ni^{2+}}$, a_{OH^-} and K_{sp} for these solutions are shown in Table I.

Solubility in Acetic Acid and Sodium Acetate Mixtures.—Nickel acetate dissociates according to the following mechanism (this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 735):

where C is the molar concentration of nickel acetate and β is the degree of dissociation of $NiAc^+$. According to this mechanism $a_{Ni^{2+}} = \beta C f_{\pm}^{\dagger}$, where $f_{\pm}^{\dagger}$ is the activity coefficient of nickel ion. The total acetate ion concentration is $C(3+\beta)$ and a_{Ac^-} (activity of acetate ion) = $C(3+\beta)f_{\pm}$, where $f_{\pm}$ is the activity coefficient of acetate ion. Assuming the activity coefficient of $NiAc^+$ to be the same as that of Ac^- at the same ionic strength, we have

$$K_2 = \frac{C\beta(3+\beta)f_{\pm}^{\dagger}}{(1-\beta)} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

Knowing the value of K_2 (*loc. cit.*) to be 7.4×10^{-2} and C , the value of β and $f_{\pm}^{\dagger}$ are calculated by the method of approximation, as in papers reported earlier, till a constant value of β and $f_{\pm}^{\dagger}$ are found. The activity of nickel ion is calculated from the final value of β and $f_{\pm}^{\dagger}$. The activity of hydroxyl ion is calculated on the same basis as in the

previous case. The calculated values of $a_{Ni^{2+}}$, a_{OH^-} and K_{sp} for these solutions are shown in Table II.

The absence of agreement in the values of K_{sp} (Table I), calculated from the solubility of nickel hydroxide in HCl, might be due to the incomplete dissociation of nickel chloride. The values of K_{sp} , obtained from buffer solutions of acetic acid and sodium acetate, are more concordant (Table II), and on account of uncertainty in complete dissociation of nickel chloride, the mean of the buffer solution values may be taken to be the correct value.

There is a wide difference between our value and Britton's reported value (*loc. cit.*). Britton used the concentration of nickel and the hydroxide when the first precipitation appeared. Some basic nickel chloride must have come down in the experiments of Britton, because, when insufficient amount of alkali is added to nickel chloride, basic salt is precipitated. Moreover, by oversight Britton took the moles of nickel in solution to be equal to half the moles of alkali added. The calculated solubility product of nickel hydroxide in his experiments, except at the initial stage of precipitation, should be the same throughout. Table III records recalculated values of solubility product in Britton's experiment. The values of the solubility product, except in the beginning when the precipitation begins and towards the end when the precipitation is getting completed, are nearly the same as our values.

TABLE III
Britton's experiment.

Alkali added	p_H	p_{OH}	Recalculated value of	
			g. mols of nickel ion per litre of soln.	solubility product of nickel hydroxide (K_{sp}).
* 0.8 c.c.	6.82	7.32	2.412×10^{-2}	5.6×10^{-17}
10.0	7.00	7.14	1.833×10^{-2}	1.3×10^{-16}
15.0	7.07	7.07	1.543×10^{-2}	1.1×10^{-16}
30.0	7.42	6.72	8.455×10^{-3}	3.1×10^{-16}
40.0	7.75	6.39	4.043×10^{-3}	6.8×10^{-16}
43.5	9.80	4.34	1.466×10^{-3}	3.1×10^{-12}

* Precipitation begins.

Like us, Gayer and Garrett also determined the solubility product of the hydroxide by dissolving nickel hydroxide in hydrochloric acid solutions (*loc. cit.*). Our solubility values agree with Gayer and Garrett's values. Our p_H values agree with Britton's values which were measured with hydrogen electrode. Our K_{sp} values also are of the same order as the corrected values of Britton, but the value of Gayer and Garrett is much lower. There appears to be some error in the measurement of the p_H values of Gayer and Garrett (*loc. cit.*).

Considering Britton's measurements and our measurements, we think that the most appropriate value of K_{sp} for nickel hydroxide would be 1.0×10^{-16} .